

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Literature review: Work music in reducing work stress

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Abstract

High productivity allows companies to produce goods and services at lower costs, so they can offer more competitive prices in the market. Productivity may experience a decline which can have a negative impact on organizational performance. Decreased productivity can be caused by prolonged work stress. This research aims to analyze the role of work music in reducing work stress. This research was carried out using the method literature *review* by determining inclusion and exclusion criteria using PICOS (Problem, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study design) from 7 articles that met the eligibility criteria, then data extraction was carried out by evaluating work music in reducing work stress. Based on the results of a systematic review conducted, it shows that the occupational safety and health program in the form of providing work music is able to increase worker productivity found in various types of work so that it can optimally increase the profits of the employing agency.

Keywords: Productivity; Work Music; Work Stress; Health Program; Occupational Safety

1. Introduction

In the era of globalization and increasingly fierce business competition, increasing productivity has become very important to ensure the survival and growth of organizations [1]. High productivity allows companies to produce goods and services at lower costs, thereby offering more competitive prices in the market. Productivity is one of the key factors that determines the competitiveness and success of an organization or company. Productivity refers to the ratio between output (goods or services produced) and input (resources used) in the production process [2]. However, in some cases, productivity can decrease which can have a negative impact on organizational performance.

Decreased productivity can be caused by various factors, one of which is work stress. Productivity and work stress are two things that are interrelated in the modern work environment. Prolonged work stress can have a negative impact on employee productivity. According to previous research, chronic stress can cause a decrease in employee concentration, motivation and performance. Apart from that, stress is also related to increased absenteeism and employee turnover, which of course can disrupt overall organizational productivity [3]. On the other hand, a productive and efficient work environment can also be a source of stress for employees. The demand to continuously increase productivity, pressure to meet targets, and excessive workload can trigger stress and fatigue in employees [4].

Stress in the workplace is a fairly big problem and often occurs in various organizations and companies in the world. According to the American Institute of Stress, approximately 83% of workers in the United States report experiencing work-related stress, and one-third experience severe stress [5]. In the UK, the Health and Safety Executive (HSE) reports that in 2021/2022, there were 914,000 cases of work-related stress, depression or anxiety. It accounts for 51% of all reported cases of occupational diseases [6].

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Meanwhile in Australia, according to a report from Safe Work Australia, in 2019-2020 there were 7,200 claims for compensation related to stress or mental health problems due to work [7]. In Indonesia, data regarding the magnitude of stress cases in the workplace is still limited. However, a study by the University of Indonesia in 2019 found that around 60% of employees in Jakarta experienced work stress [8].

Preventing stress in the workplace can be done by implementing or providing stress management training programs [9]. Implementation of training programs can be done by providing work music in the workplace. Listening to music while working can help reduce stress and increase productivity. Music can influence a person's mood, emotions and energy levels. Several studies have found that listening to music you like can reduce levels of stress hormones such as cortisol and adrenaline, as well as increase the production of dopamine and serotonin which are associated with feelings of calm and happiness [10].

Apart from that, music can also help increase concentration and focus while working. Previous studies explored the use of music in the workplace and its impact on stress [11]. Through a survey of 354 workers, this research found that most participants thought listening to music at work could reduce stress, increase productivity and create a more pleasant atmosphere. Another study examined the effect of listening to music on work stress in nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic [12]. The results showed that listening to music significantly reduced stress and fatigue levels in nurses who were facing high work pressure during the pandemic.

By considering individual preferences and type of work, work music can be a strategy to improve employee well-being, concentration, creativity and productivity in the workplace. Based on the company's need to increase labor productivity and the possibility of boredom and work stress being felt, the author created a literature review which aims to analyze the influence of work music on labor productivity.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

Literature review was carried out between 6-8 May 2024. Researchers conducted a systematic literature review of published primary and scientific literature regarding the relationship between work music in reducing stress in the workplace using the PRISMA methodology and the benefits obtained from implementing work music to reduce stress in the workplace.

2.2. Search Strategy

This research was conducted using the literature review method. The strategy for conducting a literature review is very planned and structured so that this method is very different from methods that simply convey literature studies. The data sources in this research were obtained from several databases consisting of *Google Scholar*, *Garuda Journal*, *PubMed*, and *Neliti* with similar research topics. Then the articles were sorted based on inclusion and exclusion criteria to obtain a total of 7 research articles about work music in reducing stress in the workplace.

2.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Standards

Determination of inclusion and exclusion criteria using PICOS (Problem, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study design). The main inclusion criteria of this study refer to work music in reducing stress in the workplace. This database search excluded reviews, opinion pieces, letters to the editor, commentaries, abstracts, conferences, and articles that did not focus on work distractions in reducing workplace stress.

Searches across all databases yielded 46 articles: Google Scholar (n = 22), Garuda Journal (n = 14), PubMed (n = 7), and Neliti (n = 3). Based on this data, there were 39 articles that were not relevant, so these articles were removed. A summary of the results of each database search is summarized in Figure 1 as a PRISMA flow diagram.

2.4. Data Extraction

This study carried out data extraction after articles were found that met the research inclusion and exclusion criteria. The process of mapping information taken from research articles to answer research questions. A total of 7 articles will be extracted from each article, including the year the article was published, title, author, etc.

3. Results

3.1. Research Processing

A flow diagram summarizing the study selection process is shown in figure 1. A total of 46 potentially relevant articles were identified using search strategies from various journal article sites. There were 20 studies remaining after excluding duplicates. Then, after screening titles and abstracts, the study excluded 8 other journals that did not meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria related to work music and stress. After scanning all the main sections of the 12 articles, it was discovered that another 5 articles were excluded. Finally, there were 7 articles used because they met the eligibility criteria.

Figure 1 Flowchart of Data Search Analysis of Work Music in Reducing Work Stress

3.2. Results of Literature Review Analysis of Work Music in Reducing Work Stress

There are 7 studies that discuss work music in reducing stress in the workplace. The combined results provide information regarding the effectiveness of work music, its use/application, research methods carried out, its utilization, and the results obtained from research that has been carried out. This can be seen in table 1 which summarizes the findings.

Table 1 Result of Literature Review Analysis of Work Music in Reducing Work Stress

Author	Year	Method	Results
Rozaq [13]	2019	Cross sectional	The result of this research was the discovery of a significant relationship between the application of music and the incidence of work stress. The research results show that workers' acceptance of Islamic work music is in the high category (52.5%) or even very high (45%). The incidence of work stress among respondents in the mild work stress category (72.5%).
Khadijah [14]	2022	Descriptive qualitative	The research results found that music therapy was effective in reducing stress and anxiety levels. This research is in accordance with previous research which has shown that music can influence a person's feelings, thoughts and physical condition. There were 12 respondents in the positive category.
Lidyansyah [15]	2014	Pre-experimental	There was a significant difference in scores before and after being treated with listening to music. The research results show a Z value = -2.032 and a p value = 0.042, where these results state that there is a difference in work stress scores before and after music listening behavior.
Galingging et al. [16]	2024	Quasi experimental	The results of this study show that listening to music can reduce stress levels from the moderate stress category to relaxation.
Erina et al. [17]	2020	Pre-experimental	The results of the paired sample t-test show a value of $p < \alpha 0.000$ or $p < \alpha 0.05$. It can be said that there is a difference in the level of work stress before and after being given music therapy, music therapy is effective in reducing work stress.
Wiyani et al. [18]	2021	Quasi experimental	The posttest difference test between groups obtained a p-value of 0.630. The results show the influence of a combination of progressive muscle relaxation and music therapy on work stress.
Elijah [19]	2017	Quasi experimental	The statistical test results obtained a P-value = $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. It can be said that there is an influence of music therapy on stress.

4. Discussion

Based on the 7 articles discussed in table 1, the application of the Work Music or listening to music at work can be an effective strategy for reducing work stress. The mechanism behind the effect of music in reducing stress involves several factors, namely internal and external factors. These internal factors include each individual's musical preferences and the type of work carried out by that individual. Organizations can conduct surveys or discussions to find out the type of music that workers like and also observe the work that has been done. Research shows that the type of music influences stress levels in nurses [16]. This research explains that the BmT music genre is able to reduce stress levels in nurses.

Internal factors also have a big influence on the application of work music, one of which is the work environment and work culture. Work environments can be divided into closed and open work environments. There needs to be adjustments regarding the volume level of work music to the work environment. Apart from that, work culture is also closely related to the environment in which one works. This is in accordance with research that conducted a study on farmers in Bali [18]. The results show that playing traditional Balinese work music is able to provide progressive muscle relaxation against the stress experienced by farmers.

The method of listening to music continuously will reduce work stress, can increase enthusiasm, reduce boredom at work and motivate you to work again. Music itself can reduce employee work stress levels because music can provide calm, encourage and play a role in influencing emotions and feelings. In line with research conducted on students starting from 2019-2022, the results show that the application of music is effective in reducing stress and anxiety levels [14]. Most students are in the positive category, namely it can reduce stress and anxiety.

5. Conclusion

This literature review supports previous studies which state that work music can reduce work stress. The results of this literature review can be a suggestion that music can be used as an approach in helping individuals who experience

stress and anxiety in the workplace to improve.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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